

Tiny plastics, big problem

Micro- and nanoplastics are widespread in food, water, air and the environment. They originate from plastic waste, industries or cosmetics and lead to ingestion via food, inhalation of contaminated air or dermal contact. Once in the body, they can cross barriers and end up in several organs and cells.

The harmful effects of plastics have already been confirmed in various cell types such as colon cells, hepatocytes and alveolar cells. However, research on their toxicity to the reproductive system remains limited, despite evidence of plastics being detected in reproductive organs and fluids. This raises a significant concern:

What are the effects of nanoplastic exposure on semen cells?

Multi-Method Magic: Research approach

This study aimed to explore the potential toxicity of nanoplastics, including polystyrene (PS, 60 nm), polypropylene (PP, 288 nm) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET, 210 nm), on male reproductive cells. Silica particles with comparable diameters were consulted as particle control. Boar semen cells, here considered as a representative model for mammalian semen cells, were used to evaluate the impacts on semen cell viability, motility and mitochondrial metabolism. This was assessed using the following four approaches, each providing its insights into the cell's metabolic state.

Seahorse XF Pro analysis

- Oxygen consumption (OCR)
- Extracellular acidification (ECAR)

Phase contrast microscopy

- Semen motility
- Cell viability

CASA analysis

- Semen motility
- Quantitative parameters
- Proportion static, slow, medium and rapid cells

Flow cytometry

- Mitochondrial activity
- Cell viability
- Proportion dead and mitochondrial (in)active cells

The Seahorse analysis served as the primary method for investigating the potential toxic effects of nanoplastic exposure on semen cells, whereafter results were validated using the additional approaches at multiple time points (0h, 1h and 2h after particle administration).

Results

Results are shown for PS and amino-modified PS (PS-AM) particle exposure at different concentrations. Mean OCR values obtained from the Seahorse analysis were converted to Area Under the Curve (AUC) values (Figure 1). All samples show decreased oxygen consumption upon PS exposure. Cells were split up in four categories after the flow cytometry analysis according to their metabolic state (Figure 2). An increase in the proportion of dead cells is seen upon PS-AM exposure. Following the CASA analysis, cells were categorised according to their motility (Figure 3). Samples exposed to PS showed an increased proportion of static cells. Cells treated with PP, PET and silica particles were analysed similarly. Nevertheless, exposure to these particles demonstrated a less pronounced impact compared to PS particles, requiring deeper investigation.

Figure 1. Area Under the Curve (AUC) values of the Oxygen Consumption Rate (OCR) derived from the Seahorse analysis upon PS exposure.

Figure 2. Proportion of dead and mitochondrial (in)active cells upon PS exposure determined by flow cytometry.

Figure 3. Motility percentages upon PS exposure determined by CASA.

Conclusion

The combination of the four approaches showed that the PS nanoparticles were found to exhibit a toxic impact on boar semen cell viability, motility and mitochondrial metabolism at administered concentrations of 10²-10⁴ particles/mL. Additionally, the assays revealed enhanced toxicity upon amino-modification of the PS particles. Results for PET, PP and silica particles were less clear and consistent. Findings of the Seahorse analysis showed similar or increased OCR and ECAR values upon exposure to these particles, whereas flow cytometry and CASA showed increased proportions of mitochondrial inactive and static cells, respectively. Therefore, further refinement will be crucial for more precise and comprehensive toxicity assessments in case of PET, PP and silica particles.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the help of Dr. Guilherme Rizzoto, MSc. Juri Gnagnarelli, MSc. Kristel Demeyere and professors Ann Van Soom & Evelyne Meyer. We also acknowledge the UGent core facility Flow Cytometry, Ghent University's Special Research Fund for the Seahorse equipment under grant BOF.BAS.2020.0035.01 and Research Foundation Flanders for grant G000123N that allowed procurement of Incucyte SX5. Lastly, ImpTox project which was sponsored by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant No. 965173

